

Title

Gendered Knowledge Production in García Lorca Studies: A Bibliometric Mapping

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Abstract

Federico García Lorca (FGL) was a prominent poet and playwright in 20th-century Spanish literature. García Lorca, known for his defense of the role of women in a society that historically marginalized them, built strong female characters and critics of traditional roles. This study examines the relationship between gender and the selection of research topics on Federico García Lorca, an area that remains underexplored. To fill this gap, we analyze the keywords used by authors in publications indexed in two major bibliographic databases: Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus. We construct cognitive maps that identify six key research areas within the scientific literature related to FGL. We then present a comparative analysis that examines how studies of Lorca's work have developed from a gender perspective. This approach highlights the increasing contributions of female scholars in a traditionally male-dominated field. We hope that this study will contribute to expanding the literature on how to analyze the influence of gender in the selection of research topics and the type of knowledge generated.

Keywords: *Federico García Lorca; gender perspective; bibliometric; WoS; Scopus.*

Statements and Declarations

- The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.
- The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.
- All authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with a financial or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.
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Authors contributions

- Eduardo Ruiz-Baena: Data curation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Project administration, Writing – original draft.
- Benjamín Vargas-Quesada: Data curation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Project administration, Visualization, Writing – review & editing.
- Zaida Chinchilla-Rodríguez: Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Gendered Knowledge Production in García Lorca Studies: A Bibliometric Mapping

Abstract

Federico García Lorca (FGL) is a central figure in 20th-century Spanish literature whose work challenges socially constructed notions of gender and questions traditional female roles. This article analyzes how gender influences the selection of research topics on FGL through a bibliometric study of publications indexed in Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus. The analysis incorporates recent contributions from feminist scholarship, including evidence regarding the interdisciplinary dispersion of gender-related research. Through keyword processing and cognitive mapping, the study identifies six core research areas within the scientific literature on FGL. It also investigates how datafication frameworks and metric practices may reproduce structural biases, situating the findings within contemporary debates on epistemic injustice. The results reveal increasing participation of female researchers in a historically male-dominated field, while also highlighting the persistent limitations derived from their underrepresentation in global academia. Collectively, the findings underscore the value of integrating feminist perspectives into bibliometric analyses to better understand knowledge production in the humanities.

Keywords: Federico García Lorca; gender perspective; bibliometrics; WoS; Scopus.

1. Introduction

The defense of freedom, gender equality, and marginalized groups on ideological, sexual orientation, or racial grounds by Federico García Lorca (FGL) has positioned him as a key figure for the LGBTQ+ community, ethnic minorities such as the Roma, and advocates for gender equality. His politicized figure, combined with the cultural and historical significance of his work, continues to inspire a wide range of scholarly research.

This study introduces a novel approach to analyzing research on García Lorca by examining the selection of research themes through a gender-informed perspective within academic discourse. We apply bibliometric analysis techniques

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to map the cognitive structure of the scientific production on Lorca and to provide a systematic view of its evolution over time.

Through mapping techniques, the contributions of female researchers are visualized using data from Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus. The comparative gender analysis provides a systematic perspective on how women and men have participated in shaping the field. The study offers an overview of the evolution of Lorca research and identifies authorship patterns and emerging themes over time. Despite the breadth and diversity of Lorca studies, there is still a lack of a systematic vision that examines how this field has evolved over time and, in particular, how themes are distributed from a gender perspective. Previous research has focused primarily on qualitative analyses and textual approaches, but we lack a global map that allows us to understand the intellectual development of the field as a collective object. Likewise, the gender dimension, although present in some critical works, has not been addressed from a quantitative perspective that allows evaluation of the extent to which the incorporation of female researchers has modified the themes, approaches, and critical sensibilities of the field. This absence of integrated analysis limits our understanding of the field's development and the thematic distribution when considered from a gender perspective.

2. Background

To address this gap and to contextualize the types of knowledge being produced, this study integrates bibliometric methods with contributions from feminist epistemology. This combined framework allows for situating the analysis of authorship patterns and research themes within an approach that recognizes the social and contextual dimensions of academic production. Based on this approach, we examine the theoretical conditions that help explain how literary fields are configured and how dynamics of participation and recognition influence their evolution over time.

2.1 Bibliometric analytical approaches

Throughout the last few decades, a range of bibliometric approaches have been developed to analyze the cognitive and social structure of scientific fields. Among them, co-word analysis (Callon, et al. 1983; 1991) has become a foundational tool for identifying thematic cores, emerging dynamics, and cognitive configurations

1 within a domain. Its capacity to represent conceptual organization and the
2 relationships between topics makes it an especially suitable method for studying
3 complex and evolving scientific domains, such as Lorca studies. Complementarily,
4 the CAMEOs proposed by White and McCain (1990, 2000) and expanded by White
5 (2002) allow for representing the position of authors within their academic
6 ecosystems, identifying communities, centers of influence, and co-authorship
7 patterns, which contributes an actor-oriented perspective on the field's structure.
8 Finally, overlay maps, originally developed by Leydesdorff and Rafols (2009),
9 make it possible to superimpose empirical information onto global science maps to
10 examine the distribution and evolution of research in longitudinal and comparative
11 terms (Vargas Quesada et al., 2023) have shown the potential of overlay maps to
12 represent the dynamic evolution of scientific disciplines.
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22 Taken together, these bibliometric approaches allow for mapping the
23 cognitive and social structure of a field, as well as its evolution over time. However,
24 their application usually focuses on descriptive patterns, leaving less explored their
25 articulation with theoretical frameworks that analyze the social and epistemic
26 dimensions of academic production. This study advances in that direction by
27 employing these techniques to examine how themes and authorship patterns are
28 configured in Lorca research.
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36 **2.2 The situated dimension of knowledge and authorship**

37 Academic production is not a neutral process: it is conditioned by the social,
38 disciplinary, and gender position of those who conduct research. To situate this
39 study within that framework, we turn to theories that explain how power structures
40 influence the generation and legitimization of knowledge. The notion of “situated
41 knowledges” (Haraway, 1988) rejects the idea of neutral objectivity and holds that
42 all knowledge is produced from specific perspectives. In literary fields, this
43 approach allows for understanding how the sensibilities, trajectories, or interests of
44 researchers can influence the selection of themes and approaches. This approach is
45 complemented by Standpoint Theory (Harding, 1993; Hartsock, 1983), which
46 maintains that marginalized social positions can offer epistemic advantages derived
47 from historically underrepresented experiences. This perspective allows for
48 considering how different social positions can generate distinct research priorities.
49 Likewise, the critical tradition on authorship and canon formation (Gilbert & Gubar,
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1979; Scott, 1986; Smith, 2002) has shown that literary canons are constructed through processes of selection and invisibilization that have historically tended to privilege male voices. This literature provides a useful framework for contextualizing the dynamics of participation and legitimacy in fields such as Lorca studies.

2.3 Epistemic injustice and epistemic responsibility

The concept of epistemic injustice (Fricker, 2007) offers an additional lens for understanding inequalities in knowledge production. Testimonial injustice occurs when certain voices receive less credibility due to structural prejudices; hermeneutical injustice appears when the necessary conceptual frameworks for interpreting certain experiences are lacking. These concepts allow for analyzing how certain sensibilities, themes, or perspectives may have been historically underrepresented. In parallel, the notion of epistemic responsibility (Code, 1991) underscores the ethical dimension of knowledge production, highlighting the importance of recognizing the social and political contexts that condition it. This approach supports the need to expand interpretive frameworks and integrate diverse perspectives in academic research.

2.4 Feminist critiques of data and sociotechnical infrastructures

Given that this study employs bibliometric techniques based on indexed databases, it is necessary to consider the contributions of feminist data critique and sociotechnical infrastructures. Drawing from agential realism (Barad, 2007), which posits that methods and technologies actively participate in knowledge production, to Data Feminism (D'Ignazio & Klein, 2020), these perspectives emphasize that data are not neutral and can reproduce structural biases. In this vein, authors like Noble (2018), Risam (2018), and Wernimont & Losh (2018) have shown how classification and indexing systems can contribute to the underrepresentation of certain communities, languages, or critical sensibilities. In the realm of the humanities and production in Spanish, these limitations directly affect the coverage of databases like Web of Science and Scopus. Recognizing these conditions is fundamental for adequately interpreting the bibliometric results of this study.

3. Objectives

Building on this framework this study pursues two main objectives:

a) To analyse team composition and the historical evolution of García Lorca scholarship by examining the production indexed in Web of Science and Scopus and identifying distinct temporal segments that reflect changes in the development of the field.

b) To map the thematic structure of Lorca research from a gender perspective, using bibliometric visualisation techniques to compare how male and female authors contribute to the field, particularly in terms of thematic orientations, conceptual emphases and patterns of knowledge production.

4. Methodology

4.1 Data sources and search strategy

The databases used in this study are Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus, selected for their complementary strengths. As noted by Saoualih et al. (2024), “*Scopus is characterized by its broad multidisciplinary coverage, especially in social sciences, arts and humanities, [...] whereas WoS offers robust and reliable publication metadata and impact metrics that are crucial for assessing academic trends and the influence of research.*” Together, they provide the most comprehensive basis currently available for analysing García Lorca scholarship. While both databases offer substantial coverage for the humanities, their scope is not exhaustive—particularly regarding Spanish-language publishing and certain types of scholarly outputs. These limitations are acknowledged and discussed later in the manuscript.

Data retrieval was carried out on 18 May 2024 using the following queries: WoS (Topic = “garcia-lorca”, 745 records); Scopus (TITLE-ABS-KEY-AUTH = “garcia lorca”, 379 records). No restrictions were applied regarding document type or language, in order to capture the broadest possible representation of García Lorca scholarship. Records were retained from 1946 to 2023, the latter being the most recent complete year available in both databases.

Following retrieval, the datasets from WoS and Scopus were merged and deduplicated. Duplicate detection followed a two-step procedure. First, records sharing the same DOI were automatically identified as duplicates. When no DOI was available, potential duplicates were detected by matching article title and key

1 bibliographic fields (authors, publication year and source). Because some
2 publications appear in only one of the two databases, the merging process ensured
3 that unique records from each source were retained. After merging and cleaning,
4 the final corpus comprised 891 unique publications, which constitutes the most
5 comprehensive bibliographic dataset available for analysing García Lorca research
6 across both databases from 1946 to 2023.
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10 11 12 **4.2 Temporal segmentation**

13 To ensure that the temporal segmentation was grounded in statistical evidence
14 rather than subjective judgement, several techniques for detecting structural
15 changes in the annual publication series were tested. An initial exploration using
16 second-derivative estimates proved unstable due to strong year-to-year variability
17 and the absence of a smooth underlying trend. We therefore adopted a more robust
18 procedure based on change point detection, applying the PELT algorithm (Killick
19 et al., 2012) with an RBF cost function, a method well suited for identifying
20 significant transitions in noisy time series. This approach identified two major
21 breakpoints, located in 1997–1998 and 2007–2008, marking statistically significant
22 changes in the growth dynamics of García Lorca scholarship. These breakpoints
23 provide a stable and data-driven foundation for defining the three periods used in
24 our analysis: Period 1: 1946–1997; Period 2: 1998–2007; Period 3: 2008–2023
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40 **4.3 Team composition**

41 Research teams were classified into three categories: teams composed exclusively
42 of women (Women), teams composed exclusively of men (Men), and mixed-gender
43 teams (Mixed-gender). Gender assignment was carried out manually. In cases of
44 ambiguous names or initials only, author identities were verified through online
45 searches using authorship and institutional affiliation information.
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51 From the initial dataset of 891 documents, published translations of García
52 Lorca's works were excluded. Additionally, 10 anonymous articles and 10
53 documents for which authors' gender could not be identified were removed. The
54 final corpus comprises 791 documents, of which 738 (93.3%) are single-authored
55 and 53 (6.7%) are co-authored.
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60 **4.4. Unit of analysis for mapping construction**

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Keywords were used as the primary unit of analysis to identify the cognitive structure of García Lorca scholarship. Keyword co-occurrence formed the basis of the analysis, allowing the detection of thematic relationships and research clusters. Cognitive maps were generated using VOSviewer (Van Eck et al., 2010), where nodes represent keywords (with size proportional to their frequency), links indicate co-occurrence relationships, and coloured clusters identify distinct research areas (Waltman et al., 2010). This visual approach enables the analysis of thematic configurations and their evolution over time. A thesaurus was created to normalise keywords and is publicly available at Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14811279). The base map was constructed using keywords from the 891 documents retrieved from Web of Science and Scopus and organised according to the previously defined temporal periods. Gender-based overlays were then applied to the map to visualise differences in authorship (Fig. 2). For analytical consistency, 70 publications corresponding to literal translations of García Lorca's poems were excluded. Articles co-authored by both genders (2.7% of the corpus), records for which author gender could not be identified (0.85%), and unsigned editorials (0.85%) were also removed. The final dataset comprises 455 articles authored by 350 male researchers (58%) and 329 articles authored by 280 female researchers (42%).

5. Results

The results are presented in line with the two objectives of the study. First, we analyse the historical evolution of García Lorca scholarship, including the differentiated trajectories of male and female authors and the temporal segments that shape the field. Second, we examine the thematic structure of the research through bibliometric visualisation techniques to compare how women and men contribute to the conceptual development of Lorca studies.

5.1 Authorship patterns and collaborative structures

The corpus is characterised by a strong predominance of single-authored publications, which account for approximately 94% of the total output (women: 41%; men: 59%). Co-authored works represent a small proportion of the dataset (around 6%), reflecting the traditionally individual nature of scholarship in literary studies.

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Within collaborative publications, monogendered teams are more frequent than mixed-gender collaborations. All-female teams constitute the largest share of co-authored works (34% of the total collaborative output), followed by all-male teams (24.6%). Mixed-gender collaborations account for a smaller proportion of the dataset (2.63%), indicating that cross-gender collaboration remains relatively limited in Lorca studies. Differences also emerge in team size. Collaborations composed exclusively of women are consistently organised as two-author teams, whereas all-male collaborations display greater variation, including both two-author publications and larger teams of three or four authors. Mixed-gender teams likewise range from two to four authors, suggesting a more flexible collaborative structure.

Finally, the authorship position reveals a clear gender pattern in leadership roles. Women appear as first authors in 59% of co-authored publications, compared to 41% led by men. This indicates that, when collaboration occurs, female scholars more frequently assume primary responsibility for the research, reinforcing their central role in collaborative Lorca scholarship.

5.2 Historical evolution of García Lorca scholarship (1946–2023)

The temporal analysis of publications indexed in WoS and Scopus reveals a clear developmental trajectory in García Lorca scholarship, moving from an incipient and highly masculinized field to a consolidated, diverse and globally visible research domain. The change-point detection procedure identified three statistically robust periods (Fig. 1), each reflecting distinct dynamics in the growth and organization of the field.

Fig. 1. Temporal evolution of publications with the three delimited periods.

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Period 1: Foundational and Low-Intensity Phase (1946–1997). This stage is characterised by scarce and dispersed production, corresponding to the formative phase of Lorca studies. The academic canon developed during these decades was shaped mainly by historicist and philological approaches. A methodological limitation emerges in this period: although some publications include author-provided keywords, many do not, likely reflecting heterogeneous editorial practices over several decades. A systematic examination of article-level characteristics would be required to determine the exact cause, but such analysis falls beyond the scope of this study. Given this irregular and often incomplete keyword metadata, it is not feasible to construct a reliable thematic co-word network for this foundational phase.

Period 2: Transitional Growth Phase (1998–2007). This period functions as a transitional stage marked by moderate yet uneven growth. Although the historicist and philological approaches that dominated the earlier decades remained influential, the field began to show signs of thematic renewal, with the gradual introduction of new interpretative perspectives and a growing international interest in Lorca’s work. Research lines diversified modestly during these years, signaling the shift towards the broader expansion and conceptual transformation that would characterize the following period.

Period 3: Consolidated Expansion Phase (2008–2023). This phase corresponds to the major expansion of Lorca studies. Production increased steadily and the field diversified significantly, incorporating new lines of inquiry influenced by the affective turn, queer studies, digital humanities and a broader internationalization of research.

5.3. Gendered participation over time

5.3.1 The evolution of the production of women researchers

During the first period (1946–1997), women remained almost entirely absent from formal academic production on Lorca, which meant that the early canon was established without their perspectives. From 1976 onwards, women began to appear in the record, although their presence remained minimal and largely marginal throughout the 1980s and 1990s.

The second period (1998–2007) marks a turning point. Women entered the field more frequently, ceasing to be an exception. Their contributions introduced

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new thematic sensibilities and alternative interpretative frameworks that challenged the predominant philological and historicist approaches. Although still fewer in number than men, women displayed a clear upward trend, laying the groundwork for the paradigm shift that would occur in the following decade.

The third period (2008–2023) represents a moment of consolidation and leadership for women researchers. From 2008 onwards, women surpassed men in annual output for the first time. Beyond achieving numerical parity and later superiority, they played a central role in the diversification of the field, especially in areas related to the body, affect, gender, performativity and contemporary critical theory.

5.3.2 The evolution of the production of men researchers

During the foundational period (1946–1997), male researchers dominated the field almost entirely, establishing the official contours of Lorca studies. Their work focused on biography, textual criticism and historicist interpretations, thereby shaping a canon aligned with traditional literary scholarship.

In the transitional period (1998–2007), men remained the numerical majority, although their dominance started to erode as the field opened to new perspectives. Some male scholars continued to cultivate classical lines of inquiry, while others began to incorporate more international or diversified approaches. However, the pace at which they integrated new critical frameworks was slower than among their female counterparts.

In the consolidated expansion period (2008–2023), male output stabilised. Although there was a slight numerical increase between 2020 and 2023, their thematic focus gravitated mainly toward philosophy, aesthetics, surrealism and revisitations of political history (Civil War, censorship). In contrast to women—who engaged more strongly with experiential, embodied and political readings—men tended to maintain more abstract or historiographical orientations.

5.3.3 Thematic profiles in mixed-gender research

Mixed-gender collaborations exhibit a thematic configuration that differs from single-gender authorship. Rather than reinforcing consolidated thematic cores, these teams tend to activate research fronts related to transnational circulation, geopolitical contexts and cultural mediation. Their keyword profiles are primarily

1 anchored in Front 2 (*Avant-garde, Interculturality and Memory*) and Front 5
2 (*Modern poetry, historical memory and transnational networks*), with terms such
3 as *translation, reception, coloniality of power, propaganda* and *decolonising*. This
4 orientation situates Lorca within global and comparative frameworks, emphasising
5 circulation, memory and political contexts beyond the national canon.
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41 **Fig. 2.** Global research on Lorca's oeuvre and research by gender. A) Global map:
42 <https://tinyurl.com/34z5xdyt>; B) Male overlay: <https://tinyurl.com/47h42hjt>; C) Female overlay:
43 <https://tinyurl.com/mu873svt>; and D) Mixed team overlay: <https://tinyurl.com/38acvdss> Note:
44 Through the links inserted in each figure, you can access the VOSviewer application online and
45 interact with each of the maps.
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From a longitudinal perspective, the thematic orientation of mixed-gender teams shows a clear evolution over time. In the early phase, when mixed collaboration was still marginal, their thematic focus largely aligned with the canonical axes of Lorca criticism, centring on major works, biographical approaches and early reception studies. As mixed-gender teams became more visible during the transitional period, their research expanded towards more comparative and context-sensitive approaches, incorporating analyses of theatrical reception, staging and the relationship between Lorca's work and its historical and

1 social context. In the most recent phase, mixed-gender collaborations display
2 marked thematic diversification and a stronger engagement with contemporary
3 theoretical frameworks, particularly gender and sexuality studies, cultural and
4 digital approaches, and renewed perspectives on historical and political memory
5 related to the Spanish Civil War. In this sense, mixed-gender teams function as
6 connective and transformative spaces within the research landscape, contributing to
7 the internationalisation and conceptual renewal of Lorca studies.
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11 In Front 3, “*Philosophy, aesthetics, and cinema*” (blue), an existential,
12 psychoanalytic and philosophical reading of the works is indicated, focused on
13 desire, death, the repressed and the unconscious with terms such as death drive,
14 unconscious, depth psychology, narcissism, sadomasochism, eroticism, fear,
15 thanatos, CG Jung, Sigmund Freud, Sabina Spielrein, Heinz Kohut, Nietzsche,
16 Husserl, Marc Richir. “Aesthetics” covers both artistic creation and reflection on
17 the languages of expression, from poetry to cinema and theater with a look at the
18 involvement of some authors and the aesthetics of the avant-garde movements to
19 which they belonged. Words like aesthetics, aesthetics surrealism, architecture,
20 mise-en-abyme, metatheater, literary city, theory of the duende (teoría del duende),
21 ode to Salvador Dalí, prose poems, greguería, metaphysics of art, Max Aub,
22 modernism, postmodernism. In this front, keywords like auteur cinema, cinematic
23 shamanism, contemplative cinema, Luis Buñuel, Buster Keaton, Ingmar Bergman,
24 Francis Ford Coppola, Martin Scorsese, movies, spanish silent film, anamorphosis,
25 hallucination, space, etc., are also grouped and connected, which define a critical
26 attention to cinema as an expressive medium, including both cinematographic
27 influences on García Lorca and its visual appropriation and adaptations.
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31 In Front 4, “*Theater, identity and values*” (yellow), the terms clearly connect
32 around stage representation, intermedial adaptations, and cultural identity, all in
33 dialogue with religious, philosophical, and political thought. The stage and
34 dramaturgical dimension of Lorca's works and their contemporary reinterpretation
35 in various formats is reflected in the use of keywords such as theatre practice, mise-
36 en-scène, drama, performance, stage sculpture, puppet theater, sacramental play,
37 theatricality, literary script, adaptation, film adaptation, national theatre, twentieth-
38 century spanish drama, retablillo de Don Cristóbal, Amor don Perlimplín, Doña
39 Rosita la soltera, Don Cristóbal y la Señá Rosita, La vida es sueño, Calderón de la
40 Barca, Shakespeare, etc. Another grouping of words focuses on how the plays and
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their adaptations address identity, otherness, and social and cultural tensions. As is the case with words like diaspora, Roma community, jewishness, anti-semitism, regional identity, national identity, heteronormativity, manhood crisis, identity construction, cultural assimilation, andalucian television, caribbean, spanish dance, spanish cinema, black performance. The mention of ‘values’ is due to the interest shown in the religious and philosophical values present in Lorca's works or in their rereadings, with special attention to symbolism and the ethics of meaning, which are embodied in words like christianity, eucharist, sacrifice, transubstantiation, auto sacramental, roman catholicism, enlightenment, hermeneutics, translation ethics, dialectic, Ortega y Gasset, and Goethe's Faust.

In front 5, “*Modern poetry, historical memory and transnational networks*” (violet), shows how García Lorca's poetry reflects a productive tension between poetic innovation and continuity with historical models, with special attention to poetic forms, images, and styles. It includes terms such as modern poetry, literary tradition, pastoral elegy, dramatic monologue, canon, Garcilaso, Rimbaud, Walt Whitman, Arthur Rimbaud, Stefan George, Jack Spicer, Nicanor Parra, Bob Dylan, objective correlative, metaphorical engine, and verbal imagination. In this regard, he also focuses on political activism and historical and cultural memory, especially in relation to revolutionary contexts, exile, and cultural resistance. This is reflected in keywords such as Spanish Civil War, anti-fascism, nueva canción chilena, songs of the Spanish Civil War (canciones de la Guerra Civil española), emergency theater, Chile, Soviet Union, Cyprus, Rolando Alarcón, Diego Rivera, Miklós Radnóti, Manuel Altolaguirre, and Winnipeg. And in another order of knowledge, there is a grouping of terms such as reception, translational norms, literary gatekeeper, authorial image, unpublished works, philosophical body, Paris, Latin America, Russia, Sweden, Cyprus, Poulenc, Geoffrey Parsons, Vera Kuteyshikova, Lorca play-writing, queer studies, and female authors, which explore the international circulation of Lorca's work and its reinterpretation from diverse cultures, genres and languages, both from the perspective of criticism and artistic creation.

Front 6, “*Metadata and social networks*” (light blue), this front summarizes the keywords of an article that is very different from the others: it consists of the study of networks applied to the relationship of female characters in the plays Yerma and Doña Rosita, la soltera, through this method, it aims to highlight

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quantitative data resulting from the analysis of elements such as degree centrality and the measurement of the centrality of eigenvectors.

5.4 Gender-related terms across research fronts

Beyond describing the cognitive structure of the field, the map also allows us to examine how gender-related concepts are distributed across research fronts. In the previous section, we saw how the knowledge map groups keywords into six different knowledge clusters; however, not all terms referring to gender, equality, or sexuality appear in the same grouping. This is because the interdisciplinary nature of some studies or their specificity means that certain words in this grouping are distributed across several groups. Let's see how this distribution occurs below.

Front 1: “*Literature, identity, and reception*”. This front includes the majority of terms directly linked to issues of gender identity, feminism, and sexuality, such as censorship and homosexuality, eminent-maricones, gender, gender studies, homoerotic verse, homophobia, homosexual love, irish feminism, irish woman, La casa de Bernada Alba, la novia, lgbtq+, marginality, patriarchy, motherhood, otherness, queer subject, sexuality, travestied quotations, women spaces, women repression, Yerma.

Front 2: “*Avant-garde, interculturality and memory*”. This front is the most directly related to the intersectional study of gender, identity, and global representations of dissent represented by these terms: feminine agency, femininity, fertility, gender representations

Front 3: “*Philosophy, aesthetics, and cinema*”. This front is the one that provides a theoretical and aesthetic approach to queer studies and representations of the body and sexuality. The main terms are: heterosexuality, homosexuality, queer modernism, queer theory

Front 4: “*Theatre, identity and values*”. On this front, religious values are addressed, only heterosexuality is treated as an acceptable sexual orientation captured by the term Heteronormativity

Front 5: “*Modern poetry, historical memory and transnational networks*”. These keywords: female authors, queer studies, duality and homoeroticism refer to performative practices that intersect with queer studies, performance theory, and dissident gender representations.

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Front 6: “*Metadata and social networks*”. This section examines the relevance of female characters in the plots of two plays anchored in the term female main characters

5.5 Gendered thematic profiles

This section analyses gendered thematic profiles in García Lorca scholarship by examining the distribution and relative prominence of keywords in female-authored, male-authored and mixed-gender publications. Building on the cognitive structure identified through co-word mapping (Section 5.4), it explores how different authorship configurations tend to activate specific research fronts and articulate distinct epistemic orientations within the field.

5.5.1 Thematic profiles in female-authored research

Female-authored research on García Lorca displays a thematic profile characterised by both continuity with the literary canon and a progressive expansion towards interpretative frameworks centred on subjectivity, affect and cultural mediation. As shown in Figure 3, early female-authored publications (1946–2007) remain closely anchored to core literary references, with *García Lorca*, *poetry*, *music* and *theatre* occupying central positions. These keywords reflect a strong engagement with Lorca’s poetic and theatrical production, while also signalling an interest in artistic expression beyond strictly textual analysis.

In the Consolidated Expansion Phase (2008–2023), this profile becomes markedly more diversified. Alongside canonical terms such as *poetry* and *theatre*, keywords associated with symbolic, psychological and cultural interpretation gain prominence, including *teoría del duende*, *Sigmund Freud*, *life and death* and *morality*. The increased weight of *translation studies* and *generation of 27* further indicates an openness to transnational circulation and contextualisation, situating Lorca within broader intellectual and cultural networks.

Notably, the persistence of keywords related to specific works (*La casa de Bernarda Alba*, *Poeta en Nueva York*, *Romancero gitano*) suggests a sustained focus on Lorca as a central object of study rather than as a peripheral reference. Overall, female-authored research exhibits a trajectory from literary consolidation toward interpretative depth, progressively incorporating psychological, ethical and cultural dimensions that expand the scope of Lorca studies.

Fig. 3. Maps of female research on Lorca's oeuvre by period. A) Foundational and Low Intensity, and Transitional Growth Phase 1946 - 2007: <https://tinyurl.com/42tu7zbh>; B) Consolidated Expansion Phase 2008-2023: <https://tinyurl.com/ms555x4h>

1998-2007: "Transitional Growth Phase"		2008 - 2023: "Consolidated Expansion Phase"	
Label	Score	Label	Score
garcia lorca	73	garcia lorca	396
poetry	24	poetry	53
music	17	teoria del duende	49
alvaro	13	theater	47
cepeda samudio	13	sigmund freud	37
family tradition	13	translation studies	36
la casa de bernarda alba	13	poeta en nyc	34
la casa grande	13	generation of 27	32
life and death	13	romancero gitano	32
morality	13	flamenco	30

Table 1. Women's keywords with the highest score, weight by period.

5.5.2 Thematic profiles in male-authored research

Male-authored research on García Lorca presents a thematic profile marked by stronger continuity with historicist, philosophical and aesthetic traditions. As illustrated in Figure 4, publications from the early and transitional phases (1946–2007) are dominated by keywords such as *García Lorca*, *myth*, *dialectic* and *criticism*, reflecting an emphasis on symbolic construction, intellectual abstraction

and literary theory. These terms align with approaches that foreground Lorca's position within broader philosophical and literary debates.

Fig. 4. Maps of male research on Lorca's oeuvre by period. A) 'Foundational and Low Intensity, and Transitional Growth Phase (1946-2007): <https://tinyurl.com/3yevwf3u>; B) 'Consolidated Expansion Phase: 2008-2023': <https://tinyurl.com/h6bz829c>

In the Consolidated Expansion Phase (2008–2023), male-authored research expands in volume but remains thematically concentrated around historical, political and aesthetic dimensions. Keywords such as *Spanish Civil War*, *Spain*, *surrealism* and *poetry* gain substantial prominence, pointing to a sustained interest in political history, national context and avant-garde aesthetics. References to major literary figures (*Pablo Neruda*, *Luis Cernuda*, *Gaston Baquero*) further reinforce a tendency to situate Lorca within male-dominated intellectual genealogies.

Although *translation studies* and *theatre* also appear among the most prominent terms, they are less central than in female-authored research. Overall, male-authored thematic profiles privilege abstraction, historical contextualisation and aesthetic interpretation, maintaining a relatively stable conceptual core over time and exhibiting slower diversification into affective, embodied or explicitly gendered perspectives.

1998-2007: "Transitional Growth Phase"		2008 - 2023: "Consolidated Expansion Phase"	
Label	Score	Label	Score
garcia lorca	39	garcia lorca	496
myth	11	spanish civil war	63
criticim	6	poeta en nyc	60
dialectic	6	spain	55
economic	6	poetry	53
father	6	surrealism	44
fragmentation	6	teoria del duende	39
gaston baquero	6	translation studies	35
luis cernuda	6	blood wedding	34
pablo neruda	6	theater	32

Table 2. Men keywords with the highest score, weight by period.

5.5.3 Thematic profiles by authorship configuration (male-only, female-only, and mixed teams)

Mixed-gender collaborations display a distinct thematic configuration that differs from both female-only and male-only authorship profiles. Rather than reinforcing the dominant cores observed in single-gender teams, mixed teams tend to activate research fronts associated with transnational circulation, geopolitical contexts and cultural mediation.

The keyword distribution indicates that mixed-gender publications are primarily anchored in Front 2 (*Avant-garde, Interculturality and Memory*) and Front 5 (*Modern poetry, historical memory and transnational networks*). Terms such as *Coloniality of Power, propaganda, decolonising, translation and reception* suggest a strong engagement with Lorca's work as a global and historically situated phenomenon. This orientation situates Lorca beyond the national canon, emphasising processes of circulation, reinterpretation and political memory across diverse cultural contexts.

Mixed teams also contribute to the internationalisation of Lorca studies, as reflected in the presence of multilingual and transnational references (e.g. Russian, Polish and French contexts), as well as keywords linked to museums, memorial culture and comparative memory in Latin America and Southern Europe. Notably, female leadership within mixed teams appears to play a significant role in steering research towards comparative memory studies and translation as an ethical and relational practice.

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In contrast to the more consolidated thematic cores of single-gender teams, mixed-gender collaborations function as connective spaces within the cognitive map of Lorca research. They bridge literary analysis, political history and cultural circulation, reinforcing the role of collaboration as a driver of thematic openness and international networking within the field.

6. Discussion

The results of this study confirm the central premise outlined in Section 2: academic knowledge production in García Lorca studies is not neutral but structured by gendered patterns of participation that become visible through bibliometric mapping. Rather than reflecting individual thematic choices, the differentiated distributions observed across research fronts indicate the existence of distinct epistemic orientations within the field.

From a bibliometric perspective, male-authored research shows a strong tendency to consolidate established cognitive cores. This pattern is particularly visible in Front 1 (*Literature, Identity and Reception*) and Front 3 (*Philosophy, Aesthetics and Cinema*), where male overlays concentrate around historically legitimised approaches such as literary criticism, aesthetic theory and philosophical abstraction. These configurations reproduce a canon-oriented structure that presents itself as universal and methodologically neutral, a feature long discussed in feminist epistemology as characteristic of dominant knowledge positions.

In contrast, the increasing presence of female-authored research corresponds to the activation and expansion of alternative thematic areas within the cognitive map. This shift is especially evident in Front 4 (*Theatre, Identity and Values*) and Front 5 (*Modern Poetry, Historical Memory and Transnational Networks*), where female overlays intensify around keywords related to embodiment, affect, gender, subjectivity and social marginalisation. From a bibliometric standpoint, this is not a marginal diversification but a structural reconfiguration of thematic centrality, illustrating what Harding conceptualises as “strong objectivity”: the capacity of situated perspectives to expand the analytical reach of a field.

These dynamics can be interpreted through the lens of epistemic injustice. The limited presence of gendered, affective and embodied terms in earlier phases of Lorca scholarship—particularly within the dominant fronts—suggests a form of

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hermeneutical injustice, whereby available conceptual resources were insufficient to articulate key dimensions of Lorca’s work. The subsequent emergence and consolidation of these terms within specific research fronts does not merely add new topics, but alters the internal structure of the field by redefining what counts as legitimate scholarly inquiry.

Mixed-gender collaborations provide further bibliometric evidence of this process. As shown by their overlay distributions, mixed teams disproportionately activate Front 2 (*Avant-garde, Interculturality and Memory*) and Front 5, linking Lorca’s work to transnational, geopolitical and comparative contexts. Longitudinally, this pattern reflects a shift from canon-centred analyses toward research that emphasises circulation, translation and memory across cultural boundaries. From a mapping perspective, mixed teams function as connective nodes within the research landscape, facilitating thematic permeability between otherwise distinct cognitive areas.

Importantly, these findings must also be interpreted in relation to the sociotechnical infrastructures that shape bibliometric visibility. The construction of cognitive maps using Web of Science and Scopus is itself embedded in classificatory regimes that privilege certain languages, publication formats and disciplinary traditions. From a feminist data perspective, the uneven distribution of research across fronts—particularly in the case of humanities scholarship in Spanish—should therefore be read as both an empirical pattern and a reflection of infrastructural constraints. Recognising these conditions is essential for a responsible interpretation of bibliometric results.

When situated within broader analyses of gender inequality in academia, the Lorca case aligns with patterns documented in other fields, where increased female participation intersects with shifts in thematic orientation and collaboration practices. What distinguishes Lorca studies, however, is the extent to which these transformations are visible at the level of cognitive structure. The bibliometric evidence presented here demonstrates that gender-sensitive mapping can capture not only changes in participation, but also deeper epistemic realignments within a research field.

Overall, this study shows that bibliometric analysis, when combined with feminist epistemological frameworks, provides a powerful tool for examining how knowledge is structured, legitimised and transformed. In García Lorca scholarship,

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the reconfiguration of research fronts associated with female and mixed-gender authorship signals a substantive expansion of the field's interpretative horizons, enabling a more plural, reflexive and socially grounded understanding of Lorca's work.

7. Conclusions

This study analysed the historical evolution and thematic organisation of García Lorca scholarship using a gender-sensitive bibliometric approach. By combining co-word mapping, temporal segmentation and gender-based overlays, it provides a systematic and data-driven account of how the field has developed over time and how different authorship configurations contribute to its cognitive structure.

The results reveal a clear transformation of Lorca studies from a low-intensity and highly masculinised field into a consolidated and diversified research domain. This transformation is not only quantitative, reflected in publication growth and increased female participation, but also qualitative, as evidenced by the reconfiguration of research fronts and thematic orientations across distinct temporal phases.

Gender-disaggregated science maps show that male-, female- and mixed-gender authorship are associated with differentiated thematic profiles. Male-authored research tends to concentrate around established canonical and aesthetic cores, whereas female-authored research expands fronts related to embodiment, affect, gender and subjectivity. Mixed-gender collaborations play a connective role, activating transnational, comparative and memory-oriented perspectives that bridge otherwise distinct areas of the field. These patterns demonstrate that gender functions as a structuring dimension of knowledge production rather than a purely demographic variable.

From a methodological perspective, this article highlights the potential of bibliometric mapping to engage critically with literary scholarship. When combined with feminist epistemological frameworks, bibliometrics allows not only the description of research activity, but also the examination of how epistemic authority and thematic legitimacy are constructed. Beyond García Lorca studies, this approach offers a transferable framework for analysing gendered knowledge structures in other humanities fields.

8. Limitations and further research

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting its findings. First, the analysis is based on publications indexed in Web of Science and Scopus. While these databases provide structured and reliable metadata, they offer limited coverage of humanities research, particularly work published in Spanish, in local journals, or in non-indexed edited volumes. As discussed in critical data studies and feminist digital humanities, such infrastructures are not neutral but reflect editorial, linguistic and geopolitical hierarchies that shape visibility and recognition (D'Ignazio & Klein, 2020). These constraints may affect thematic representation and authorship patterns, especially in the early phases of García Lorca scholarship, and require a cautious interpretation of observed trends.

Second, the bibliometric mapping relies on keyword metadata to reconstruct the cognitive structure of the field. In the foundational period, keyword availability is uneven: while some publications include author-provided terms, many do not, plausibly reflecting historical editorial practices, although confirming this would require article-level inspection beyond the scope of this study. This limits the representation of early thematic configurations. Future research could address this limitation by applying Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to extract keywords from titles and abstracts of records lacking original metadata. The subsequent automatic indexing of these documents would increase coverage and improve the resolution of cognitive mapping, offering a more complete thematic representation of García Lorca scholarship over time.

Third, gender identification was conducted manually using bibliographic metadata and external verification. Although this approach maximises accuracy, it is time-consuming and limits scalability. Automated gender assignment was not applied due to well-documented limitations related to name ambiguity, cultural bias and binary assumptions (González-Salmón & Robinson-García, 2024). Future research could explore semi-automated workflows combining tools such as Genderize, NamSor or Gender API with targeted manual validation to reduce processing time while preserving reliability.

Future research could also examine the geographical dimension of gendered knowledge production in García Lorca studies. A transnational analysis supported by country-level cognitive maps would allow assessment of whether gender-oriented research is concentrated in specific academic contexts or distributed across

1 both central and peripheral research systems. Finally, as with all bibliometric
2 studies, this analysis relies exclusively on published output and cannot capture
3 potential biases operating at earlier stages of the editorial process, such as peer
4 review or differential rejection rates. Consequently, the inequalities observed here
5 may represent only a partial manifestation of broader structural dynamics shaping
6 academic knowledge production.
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